

POLICY BRIEF

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

WOMEN IN DEFENSE: AN APPROACH TO GENDER AND THE ARMED FORCES IN BRAZIL.

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POLICY STATEMENT

One of the most important themes for reflection in the field of defense is the gender debate. Many women have contributed to the academic area in defense, and many others have actively participated in positions in the Armed Forces. In Brazil, the number of women in the high command of the Armed Forces remains very small. However, the policies for the entry of women into military career schools have expanded this possibility. On the other hand, women, civilians, academics, and researchers in the area of Defense have helped increase women's participation in themes seen as "the exclusive male debate." Thus, in schools of higher studies in Brazil, many women are included in research and the Defense career, actively participating in projects and encouraging the inclusion of new women in the area, with multiple debates. The issue of gender and the armed forces has been studied extensively in international institutions, focusing on the participation of women in training courses, decision-making activities, and peace missions. In addition, policies to encourage women's participation have been debated within the scope of one of the most important forums, the UN.

BACKGROUND

More than 20 years ago, the UN had passed Resolution 1325 on Women, Peace, and Security [1]. In its document, it expressed the importance of women's participation in preventing and resolving conflicts, consolidating peace, and the need for women's participation in decision-making processes on an equal footing. The female representation in action in peace and peacekeeping actions, especially in the struggle of women and girls who are increasingly vulnerable in armed conflicts, brought to the UN agenda the participation of women for peace and security, being involved in all processes from the highest level of management and decision-making to the execution of peace processes.

The continuity and implementation of this agenda have followed 21 years with inclusive policies and greater participation of women in the Armed Forces. However, the discourse of gender integration has not yet managed to overcome some challenges of the masculine vision, of the dominant imposition of men, militarized, against the mentality of defense, security, and the promotion of peace in plural and more inclusive way.

A historical analysis of the inclusion of gender, its debate, and insertion of policies on the UN agenda made it possible to recognize the impact of the war on the lives of women and girls. It was noted that issues like this were not included as a theme anymore. aspects of international relations, peace processes, UN practices, and policies.[2] Therefore, the United Nations has included policies, legislation, and programs in all areas and levels addressing the role of women and giving them the effective role of peacekeepers and with high representation in decision-making.[3][4]

Policies for the inclusion of women in the labor market followed the feminist agenda and expanded the space for many to work in different sectors. Female participation in the military sector would also be included in this process, adapting to new social needs and the military role beyond the war. According to Dantas (2018), "the struggle for rights in the economic and social sphere made women seek employment opportunities and work in areas that were not available to them before, one of them being the military career, even if this was configured as voluntary work in the Forces" (DANTAS, 2018).[5]

Faced with a plurality of new military missions, including humanitarian stabilization and reconstruction missions in conflict-ravaged countries, women began to participate more frequently in military tasks, mainly by incorporating the health areas of the Forces, currently extending to other areas technicians such as social communication, teaching, etc. However, the combatant woman is still a debate in the international context and has ensured a series of debates from a sociological, physiological point of view, among others.

On this occasion, Brazil has approved changes in the career structures of the military and placed women in military academies, which are still restricted to just a few actions. This inclusion in the possibility of forming a female military corps represented an advance. Still, in the agenda for the effective participation of women in the Armed Forces, this is not the only policy to be implemented and represents a first step towards the construction of social and institutional conscience that they need to look at women as true members.

FINDINGS

Brazil has still sought to consolidate its policies of inclusion and participation of Women in the Armed Forces. Currently, the number of women remains in small percentages, and few are in the military high command. According to the Ministry of Defense, there are currently 33,960 women in the armed forces, 8413 in the Brazilian Navy, 13,009 women in the Army, 12,538 in the Air Force, and 482 women among civil servants, military, outsourced and interns in administration at the Ministry of Defense.[6]

However, the challenge is that this number represents approximately 10% of the total number of active soldiers in the Armed Forces and an even smaller number for women in high positions and ranks. It is not trivial that this current global discussion should be inserted in the research agenda and public policies that can increase the inclusion of women in the Armed Forces and the adaptation of institutions that for years were a male space to receive women with equal treatment and rights.

In 2005, intending to promote Agenda 1325, the UN Security Council recommended that the Member States develop National Plans of Action (NAPs) to encourage gender equality policies. Our PNA was only consolidated in 2017, 12 years after the UN recommendation was made. Although other domestic public policies were created during this period in the evolution of gender equality, an orientation plan marks a non-tacit political action so that measures are carried out and fulfilled for gender equality and the participation of Women in the Armed Forces and the 1325 agenda.

Brazil implemented the National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security [7] in 2017 under the coordination of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and the Alexandre Gusmão Foundation (FUNAG), in compliance with the policies oriented by the United Nations and by the global effort in the fight for rights and equality of women in various professional activities.

This plan brought the guidelines for the insertion of women and already used other documents that could implement gender participation policies in military activities. According to the document "The National Plan of Policies for Women 2013-2015 dedicated four actions related to the agenda, regarding the diagnosis of competencies for the execution of duties by women in peace missions, capacity building, and training for peace missions from a gender perspective, partnerships for the prevention of HIV/AIDS and for combating sexual violence as a weapon of war, and strategies against gender-based violence in humanitarian assistance contexts." [7]

As strategic objectives that permeated the construction of the National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security, there are two: "the mainstreaming of gender in all international peace and security actions promoted by Brazil, and the empowerment of women and girls as promoting agents of lasting peace." These objectives built public policies; however, the effective practice of their actions has been questioned even by international bodies. Currently, Brazil has not met the minimum numbers indicated by the UN for the participation of women in international actions carried out by the country, for example, the low participation of women in humanitarian missions, which has impacted the effectiveness of the plan and the continuity of policies of gender equity.

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, it is necessary to reflect on the effective actions that have been taken in the inclusion of women in the Armed Forces and within the Ministry of Defense, civilian or military, but which provide more gender equality in the debates on Security and National Defense. Brazil represents significant advances such as in the National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security. On the other hand, it becomes a step backward with government policies that do not support the perspective of balance and equity in the participation of women and men in the agenda of defense. States need to build actions that simply go beyond ideological perspectives and maintain the logic of plurality, of equality between men and women, as provided for in our Magna Carta.

SUGGESTIONS

One of the most important issues that brought the need for writing this work is that the National Action Plan on Women, Peace, and Security created in 2017 is expected to be used only until the present year. In 2022 we are expected to present a newly revised plan with new implementations for UN agenda 1325. From this perspective, promoting working groups to think about gender equality in the Armed Forces and expanding the scope of discussion present in the plan to address civilian women who make up the National Defense think tank and are also in the Ministry of Defense becomes relevant.

Another recommendation is to include a broader view on gender that addresses women in the Armed Forces and a broader debate to lessen the impacts on individuals who bring a new gender perspective and who are limited by legal issues.

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